

KISS NIGHTCLUB FIRE: CASE STUDY ON THE APPLICATION OF THE INCIDENT COMMAND SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the response to the fire that occurred at the Kiss Nightclub, located in Santa Maria, Rio Grande do Sul (Brazil), on January 27, 2013. The incident began when a spark from pyrotechnic material used during a performance hit the foam on the ceiling of the establishment, causing the rapid spread of the fire. At the time, the venue was overcrowded, with a capacity far above the permitted limit, and had only one emergency exit, which significantly worsened the severity of the tragedy. The fire resulted in the deaths of 242 people and left 680 injured, the majority of the victims dying from smoke inhalation. Due to the magnitude of the event, many victims were rescued by civilian volunteers, who acted without proper training and without the necessary personal protective equipment. The analysis focuses on the application of the Incident Command System (ICS) during the fire response. ICS is an internationally recognized methodology for emergency management, enabling the command, control, and coordination of response actions in an efficient and structured manner. To this end, the research adopts a qualitative approach based on a case study of the incident.

Keywords: Kiss nightclub, Boate Kiss, Incident Command System, Mass-Casualty Incident.

Introduction

At 3 a.m. on January 27, 2013, a fire broke out at the Kiss Nightclub, located in Santa Maria, in the state of Rio Grande do Sul (Brazil). The incident occurred during a university party, where a local band was performing. The fire started from a spark generated by a firework

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used by the band, which struck the insulation foam on the nightclub's ceiling. In less than a minute, the flames spread rapidly throughout the venue, which had only one exit for approximately 1,300 people present. The lack of proper escape routes and overcrowding resulted in the deaths of 242 people, in addition to leaving 680 injured.

The initial response to the fire was conducted by two units of the Fire Department, composed of seven military firefighters and six trainee firefighters. As the first to arrive at the scene, the team had the responsibility of properly implementing the Incident Command System (ICS), a methodology widely adopted internationally for managing incidents of various natures. In Brazil, the ICS was introduced by the Government of the State of Santa Catarina through the State Civil Defense and the Federal University of Santa Catarina, and was later adopted by other states and the Federal District.

The objective of this research is to analyze the application of the Incident Command System (ICS) in the Santa Maria Fire Department's response to the Kiss Nightclub fire. The intention is to evaluate whether the actions of the emergency teams were in accordance with the principles and guidelines of the ICS, as well as to identify any failures in the procedures adopted during the incident management. It is not the intent of this study to assign "blame" among the responders, who made extraordinary efforts to save as many victims as possible. However, from a scientific perspective, it is essential to analyze incidents to improve responses to future mass casualty events.

The relevance of this study stems from the catastrophic magnitude of the fire, which mobilized a wide network of public agencies and institutions, both state and federal, in Santa Maria. Among those involved were the Fire Department, Military Police, Medical Examiner's Office, Military Brigade, Civil Police, Federal Highway Police, State Highway Police, Mobile Emergency Care Service (SAMU), Air Base Firefighters, Municipal Guard, and the Brazilian Army, in addition to several federal and private entities. Due to its magnitude and complexity, the fire required a coordinated response from the moment the first responders arrived, using a structured system such as the ICS. However, as determined by the authorities, from the beginning of the operation, there were failures in the organization of resources and the implementation of incident command, impairing essential functions such as safety, communication, planning, operations, and logistics.

The research adopts a qualitative theoretical approach, using the case study method.

This method aims to explore the event in depth, considering its complexity and dynamism, and providing insights for critical analysis and decision-making in similar situations (ANDRÉ, 2005, p. 49). The methodology includes a specialized literature review, complemented by the analysis of reports and official documents on the incident, with the aim of constructing a detailed overview of the emergency response teams and the application of the ICS. Reports from public and private institutions, as well as news articles and documents related to the fire, were analyzed. The theoretical analysis is based on existing doctrine regarding the Incident Command System (FEMA, 2018), with emphasis on the works of Walsh (2005) and Nicholson (2033).

The nightclub

Inaugurated in 2009 by entrepreneurs Elissandro Callegaro Spohr and Mauro Londero Hoffman, the company Santo Entretenimento Ltda – ME (Boate Kiss) was located at 1925 Andradas Street, downtown Santa Maria (ÉPOCA, 2015), a city with approximately 260,000 inhabitants, situated 290 km west of Porto Alegre, in the state of Rio Grande do Sul. The venue covered an area of 638 m², and the maximum occupancy capacity was 769 people, according to data from the General Institute of Forensics of Rio Grande do Sul (IGP-RS as cited in POLÍCIA CIVIL DE SANTA MARIA - RS, p. 88).

The nightclub had two doors, each 360 cm wide, at the front. One of them was fenced off, creating a smoking area. The first fire prevention permit was issued in August 2009 by the Fire Department. This permit was renewed in 2011, with a one-year delay, and at the time of the incident, the document had expired.

The venue's soundproofing consisted of a lining made of two layers of gypsum ceiling, with two additional layers of glass wool, a flammable material made from polyurethane. When burned, this product emits hydrogen cyanide (HCN), a gas 25 times more toxic than carbon monoxide.

The nightclub had only one exit to the outside and lacked a proper emergency lighting system. In addition, the exit routes were not properly marked, the fire extinguishers were expired, and there was no sprinkler system or fire hose boxes that could allow for an effective and timely response to the fire.

The windows were obstructed, and there were guardrails and barriers along the path to

the exit, which hindered the public's quick evacuation. The report from the Regional Council of Engineering and Agriculture - RS (CREA – RS) summarized the nightclub's characteristics as follows:

o revestimento acústico inflamável foi aplicado de forma aparente no palco, sobre o revestimento original de gesso acartonado e lã de rocha. Como o palco era elevado, o contato entre os elementos pirotécnicos usados no show do Conjunto Gurizada Fandangueira e o material inflamável se tornou possível. Estavam configuradas as condições para o início do sinistro. (CREA-RS, 2013)

(The flammable acoustic insulation was visibly applied on the stage, over the original lining of drywall and rock wool. Since the stage was elevated, contact between the pyrotechnic elements used in the show by the band *Gurizada Fandangueira* and the flammable material became possible. The conditions for the fire to start were set, our translation).

The Party

A group of students from the Pedagogy, Agronomy, Veterinary Medicine, and Zootechnics courses at the Federal University of Santa Maria organized a party called *Agromerados*, which featured a performance by the band *Gurizada Fandangueira*. The event started at 11:00 PM on Saturday, January 26, 2013. It is estimated that approximately 1,300 people were present at the nightclub on the night of the fire.

Figure 1. Site Plan

Source: *NFPA Journal Latinoamericano*.

The Incident Command System (ICS)

The Incident Command System (ICS) was created in the United States in the 1970s with the aim of organizing the response of forest fire teams in California. Over time, the system evolved, becoming applicable to various types of emergencies due to its common organizational structure and standardized management by the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) in the United States.

In Brazil, the introduction of the ICS took place in the state of Santa Catarina, with the support of the State Civil Defense and the University of Santa Catarina. Later, the system was implemented by other states and the Federal District. The Manual of the Military Fire Brigade of the Federal District defines the ICS as follows:

É uma ferramenta de gerenciamento de incidentes padronizada, para todos os tipos de sinistros, que permite a seu usuário adotar uma estrutura organizacional integrada para suprir as complexidades e demandas de incidentes únicos ou múltiplos, independente das barreiras jurisdicionais (CORPO DE BOMBEIROS MILITAR - DF, 2011).

(It is a standardized incident management tool for all types of incidents, which allows its user to adopt an integrated organizational structure to meet the complexities and demands of single or multiple incidents, regardless of jurisdictional barriers, our translation).

The ICS has been considered highly reliable by researchers such as Bigley et al. and Kane (2001 apud BUCK et al., 2006). One of the advantages of this system is its ability to allow the planning of the incident response, even with the participation of multiple organizations. BUCK (2006) explains that the planning cycle creates specific objectives for each operational period, and that all entities involved in the incident response work towards achieving these objectives. He also clarifies that the plan not only contains the objectives but also the identification of each entity's responsibilities to achieve these objectives:

The planning cycle creates specific goals to attend during each operational period. In it there is a strategic or campaign plan and a tactical or action plan. In the action plan, objectives are set for each operational period. The entire set of organizations responding to an incident work toward accomplishing those objectives. The operational plan not only sets the objectives, but also identifies who is going to accomplish them (BUCK et al. 2006, p. 2).

Other authors agree that one of the benefits of the Incident Command System is reducing coordination problems and enhancing the effectiveness of the response:

In the years that followed its creation, the ICS was perceived by practitioners as successful in reducing coordination problems and improving fire response effectiveness (BIGLEY e ROBERTS 2001; BUCK, TRAINOR e AGUIRRE 2006 e COLE 2000 apud MOHYNIHAN, p.897).

During the incident at *Boate Kiss*, various public agencies in the city of Santa Maria were mobilized. Among the main ones were the Fire Department, the Military Brigade, the Civil Police, the Federal Highway Police, the State Highway Police, the Mobile Emergency Service (SAMU), the Air Base Firefighters, the Municipal Guard, the Brazilian Army, and the Forensic Institute (IML), along with other support organizations.

The incident required a coordinated response, which should have been structured from the beginning with the implementation of the Incident Command System (ICS), starting with the arrival of the first responders. This system would have facilitated the integration and coordination of the different agencies involved, optimizing resource management and communication among the various response organizations.

The Incident Command System (ICS) is an emergency management model that facilitates the coordination of multiple agencies, enabling the execution of various tasks in response to complex incidents. Its fundamental principles include: the use of common terminology, ensuring mutual understanding among all agencies involved; the definition of an efficient control span, limited to a number of 1 to 7 personnel per supervisor; the integration of communications with common frequencies and without the use of codes, ensuring clarity in transmissions; and a modular organization, allowing the structure to adapt to the magnitude of the incident in a predictable and orderly manner.

Another crucial aspect of ICS is the development of a single, consolidated Incident Action Plan, which aims to prevent duplication of efforts and waste of resources. The system also establishes a Unified Command, preventing conflicting orders and isolated initiatives, promoting the effective use of available resources. Furthermore, ICS provides for the standardization of essential facilities, such as the Incident Command Post, Operations Bases, and Waiting Areas, facilitating logistics and operational control during the incident response.

The first responder to arrive at the incident scene is responsible for initiating the Incident Command System (ICS) or transferring command to the next unit that arrives, if immediate assistance is required and structuring the command is not feasible at that moment. The installation of the Incident Command Post (ICP) and support facilities should be carried

out according to the magnitude and needs of the incident.

In mass casualty events, such as the one at Boate Kiss, it may be necessary to implement a series of additional facilities for the efficient management of the response. Among these facilities are the creation of a helipad for air transportation of the injured, a Victim Concentration Area for triage and pre-hospital treatment, a Waiting Area for rescue teams to await instructions, and a Rehabilitation Area for rescuers, in order to ensure the continuity of operations under safe and organized conditions. These measures are essential to ensure a coordinated and effective response in large-scale incidents.

The structure of the Incident Command System (ICS) is organized into two main groups: the Command Staff and the General Staff (Figures 2 and 3). The Command Staff is responsible for essential command functions, while the General Staff handles the operational management, logistics, planning, and administration of the incident.

When the incident reaches a high level of complexity, the role of the Incident Commander is replaced by a Unified Command. In this model, all agencies involved in the emergency response have representatives in the command, ensuring the integration of decisions and the effective coordination of actions among the different organizations. The Unified Command allows multiple agencies to share responsibility for controlling the incident, promoting a harmonious response and preventing leadership conflicts or overlapping efforts.

Figure 2. ICS Staff

Source: ICS Manual of the CBMDF, p. 56

Figure 3. General Staff of the ICS

Source: ICS Manual of the CBMDF, p. 60

The Incident Command System has several levels that allow the structure to grow according to the needs of the incident, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Levels of the ICS structure

Source: ICS Manual of the CBMDF, p. 72

In addition, each activity within the ICS is coordinated by a person in charge with a specific title, whose roles and responsibilities are clearly defined (Figure 4). These individuals take on distinct roles in managing the incident, ensuring that each task is carried out according to established protocols. The clarity in assignments facilitates coordination between the teams, promoting an efficient and organized response.

Figure 5. ICS Positions and Their Responsibilities

Source: ICS Manual of the CBMDF, p. 69

The Incident

At 03:15 on January 27, 2013, the fire started from the use of a Sputnik-type pyrotechnic device during a musical performance by the band *Gurizada Fandangueira*, which was playing inside the nightclub (*Ministério Público de RS*, 2013). The spark hit the foam that covered the ceiling of the venue, releasing highly toxic smoke. In less than a minute, the fire spread rapidly. The establishment had only one exit, which proved insufficient to evacuate the approximately 1,300 guests present at the event. This limitation was one of the main factors that contributed to the tragic outcome of 242 deaths and 680 injuries. Two infographics detailing the dynamics of the fire and the layout of the venue can be viewed in Annexes 1 and 2. According to the Polícia Civil report:

O produtor da banda, Luciano Augusto Bonilha Leão, responsável pelo fogo de artifício, colocou uma luva na mão no vocalista da banda, Marcelo de Jesus dos Santos, na qual estava acoplado o objeto. Posteriormente, Luciano acionou o referido fogo de artifício, mediante controle remoto. O vocalista da banda levantou a mão em direção ao teto e uma chama ou faísca tocou o forro, o qual possuía isolamento acústico de esponja, material altamente inflamável (poliuretano). Assim, poucos segundos depois a espuma pegou fogo, gerando uma fumaça preta e tóxica que se alastrou por toda a boate, circunstância comprovada pela prova testemunhal, pericial e por um vídeo de um minuto e vinte segundos, (referido no laudo pericial), extraído de um telefone celular pertencente a uma pessoa que se encontrava no interior da boate, fazendo com que muitas pessoas desmaiassem tão logo aspiraram o ar impregnado da fumaça originada da queima. Na escala de tempo deste vídeo, verifica-se que quarenta segundos depois das pessoas que portavam o telefone terem percebido que se tratava de fogo, a fumaça já havia tomado conta e o caos estava instalado no ambiente superlotado do estabelecimento. (POLÍCIA CIVIL DE SANTA MARIA – RS. 2013, p. 2-3)

(The band's producer, Luciano Augusto Bonilha Leão, responsible for the fireworks, placed a glove on the hand of the band's vocalist, Marcelo de Jesus dos Santos, to which the device was attached. Later, Luciano activated the firework via remote control. The band's vocalist raised his hand toward the ceiling, and a flame or spark touched the ceiling, which was covered with acoustic sponge insulation, a highly flammable material (polyurethane). Thus, a few seconds later, the foam caught fire, generating black and toxic smoke that spread throughout the nightclub, a circumstance confirmed by witness testimony, forensic evidence, and a one-minute-and-twenty-second video (referenced in the forensic report), extracted from a cellphone belonging to someone inside the club. This caused many people to faint as soon as they inhaled the air contaminated by the smoke from the fire. In the timeline of this video, it can be seen that forty seconds after the people holding the phone realized it was a fire, the smoke had already taken over, and chaos was established in the overcrowded environment of the venue, our translation).

Initially, some nightclub employees attempted to use fire extinguishers, but they failed, not working as expected. In a desperate effort, one of the employees tried to put out the flames using a bottle of water, without success. Additionally, when the evacuation began, some security guards mistook the situation for a general fight and, worried about the possibility of patrons leaving without paying their tabs, temporarily prevented people from exiting the nightclub.

Não bastasse a existência de uma única saída, contribuiu também para o resultado danoso a existência de diversos obstáculos físicos, guarda-corpos (barras de contenção) nas rotas de saída, degraus, deficiência da iluminação de emergência, falta de indicação ou sinalização das rotas de fuga, além do local estar superlotado, fatores que em conjunto dificultaram a rápida evacuação do local. (POLÍCIA CIVIL DE SANTA MARIA - RS, p. 3)

(As if the existence of a single exit wasn't enough, it also contributed to the harmful outcome the presence of several physical obstacles, such as guardrails (barricades) on the exit routes, steps, inadequate emergency lighting, lack of indication or signage for escape routes, and overcrowding of the venue, all contributed to the difficult and slow evacuation of the premises, our translation).

In summary, according to the report from CREA-RS, the causes of the fire were:

A combinação do uso de material de revestimento acústico inflamável, exposto na zona do palco, associada à realização de show com componentes pirotécnicos.

Analisando relatos, a propagação do incêndio, por sua vez, foi fundamentalmente influenciada pela falha de funcionamento dos extintores localizados próximos ao palco, que poderiam ter extinguido o foco inicial de incêndio.

O grande número de vítimas, por sua vez, foi influenciado pela dificuldade de desocupação, pelas deficiências nas saídas de emergência, e pelo excesso da lotação máxima permitida. A superlotação (aparentemente era comum que a casa abrigasse cerca de 1.000 pessoas, e isso parece ter ocorrido na noite do sinistro) e as características inadequadas do espaço, em termos de sinalização, tamanho e localização das saídas de emergência dificultou a evacuação.

Essas deficiências foram compostas pela aparente falta de treinamento para situação de emergências e da ausência de equipamento de comunicação da equipe de segurança do local. Tudo isso contribuiu para retardar a saída das pessoas nos minutos posteriores ao incêndio, tendo papel decisivo no número de vítimas.

(The combination of the use of flammable acoustic coating material, exposed in the stage area, along with the use of pyrotechnic components during the show.

Analyzing reports, the spread of the fire was fundamentally influenced by the malfunctioning of the fire extinguishers located near the stage, which could have extinguished the initial fire source.

The high number of victims, in turn, was influenced by the difficulty of evacuation, deficiencies in the emergency exits, and exceeding the maximum occupancy limit. Overcrowding (it was apparently common for the venue to host around 1,000 people, which seems to have been the case on the night of the incident) and the inadequate characteristics of the space, in terms of signage, size, and location of emergency exits, hindered evacuation.

These deficiencies were compounded by the apparent lack of emergency training and the absence of communication equipment for the venue's security team. All of this contributed to delaying people's exit in the minutes following the fire, playing a decisive role in the number of victims, our translation).

At 03:17, the initial response from the Fire Department consisted of two units, totaling seven military firefighters and six firefighter trainees, who were not properly prepared to handle the magnitude of the incident (ten firefighters according to the NFPA report). The Civil Police report of Santa Maria explains:

Solicitaram apoio de populares ou permitiram que civis colaborassem no resgate das vítimas. Os bombeiros não continham os civis. Empréstavam lanternas e molhavam os populares para que ingressassem no interior da KISS, permitiam que eles segurassem as mangueiras. Noutras palavras, a prova carreada aos autos bem evidencia o amadorismo e o despreparo dos bombeiros que primeiro chegaram ao local do sinistro.

Em decorrência dessas atitudes dos bombeiros, cinco pessoas morreram, pois adentraram no interior da Boate KISS desprovidos de equipamentos de proteção individual adequados no intuito de salvar amigos, familiares, namorados (as) (POLÍCIA CIVIL DE SANTA MARÍA, p. 107-108).

(They requested the support of civilians or allowed them to assist in rescuing the victims. The firefighters did not restrain the civilians. They lent flashlights and wet the civilians to allow them to enter the interior of KISS, and allowed them to hold the hoses. In other words, the evidence presented in the case clearly shows the amateurism and lack of preparedness of the firefighters who arrived first at the scene of the disaster. As a result of these actions by the firefighters, five people died, as they entered the KISS nightclub without the proper personal protective equipment in an attempt to save friends, family members, and loved ones, our translation).

A technical team from the National Fire Protection Association (NFPA) investigated the incident and provided additional details about the firefighters' response. In their report, only ten personnel are mentioned in the initial response:

Inmediatamente después de que llegan los llamados a la Central de Bomberos de Santa Maria, a las 03:17 de la mañana se despacha una unidad de extinción de incendios y otra de rescate con 10 bomberos en total, que salen desde la Estación Regional de Bomberos # 4 de esta ciudad, a 2 km de la discoteca. Dependiendo de la fuente, entre cinco y siete minutos más tarde los bomberos ya están en frente de la discoteca. Cuando los bomberos entran al lugar, unos buscan el foco del incendio y encuentran que éste ya se había auto- extinguido. Otros buscan sobrevivientes, pero ya es muy tarde. No por el tiempo de respuesta de los bomberos, sino más bien por la velocidad en que se desarrollan este tipo de incendios. A los bomberos también les llama la

atención el sonido incesante de llamadas a los celulares de las víctimas. Los bomberos encuentran el edificio lleno de humo, un humo denso y negro. Más o menos a las 04:00 de la mañana se inician las labores de salvamento. (*NFPA JOURNAL LATINOAMERICANO, 2013*)

(Immediately after the calls reached the Santa Maria Fire Department Central, at 03:17 a.m., a fire suppression unit and a rescue unit with a total of 10 firefighters were dispatched from Fire Station #4 in this city, located 2 km from the nightclub. Depending on the source, the firefighters arrived at the scene between five and seven minutes later. When they entered the nightclub, some searched for the fire's source and found that it had already self-extinguished. Others searched for survivors, but it was already too late. Not because of the firefighters' response time, but due to the rapid development of this type of fire. The firefighters were also struck by the incessant sound of the victims' cell phones ringing. They found the building filled with thick, black smoke. At approximately 04:00 a.m., rescue operations began, our translation).

Furthermore, the fire released hydrogen cyanide gas, originating from the polyurethane acoustic insulation, which is highly asphyxiating and inhibits cellular respiration, leading to death by respiratory failure within minutes.

When the first rescue unit arrived at the scene, they found around 600 to 700 people, including patrons and injured individuals, gathered at the nightclub's entrance. Faced with this situation, the unit called for support from all available teams in the region. As a result, units from the Military Brigade and Federal and State Highway Police were mobilized to assist in transporting the injured to hospitals, as the number of ambulances from both public and private services was insufficient to meet the high demand for victims. (PC – RS, p. 109)

Due to the difficulty of accessing the interior of the nightclub, the firefighters requested civilian assistance to break down walls with sledgehammers in an attempt to establish quick entry. However, many civilians who participated in the search and rescue inside the venue were not properly trained and lacked the necessary personal protective equipment (PPE) to deal with the hazardous situation. According to testimonies, the firefighters would wet the volunteers' shirts or the volunteers themselves in an attempt to provide some form of protection against the flames, allowing them to enter the building (Photos 1 to 3). Despite the heroic efforts of these volunteers, many perished from smoke inhalation after rescuing several victims.

Em determinado momento, o declarante pegou a mangueira dos Bombeiros, que estava com o civil e avançou com ela em direção ao fundo do prédio, para jogar água o mais longe que pudesse, sem ser advertido pelos Bombeiros; em certa oportunidade, o declarante pegou um Bombeiro que estava próximo à porta e disse: “vamos entrar lá e salvar as pessoas;” após, o declarante pegou o referido Bombeiro

pelo braço e entrou com ele no prédio; resgataram uma vítima e o tal Bombeiro, após saírem do prédio, se afastou do declarante e não entrou mais no prédio; acha que ele ficou com medo de que o declarante o obrigasse a retornar ao interior do prédio. (PC - RS, p. 111)

(At a certain point, the declarant took the firefighters' hose, which was in the hands of a civilian, and advanced with it towards the back of the building, trying to spray water as far as possible, without being warned by the firefighters; on one occasion, the declarant grabbed a firefighter who was near the door and said, "Let's go in there and save the people;" then, the declarant took the mentioned firefighter by the arm and entered the building with him; they rescued a victim, and after exiting the building, the firefighter distanced himself from the declarant and did not enter the building again; the declarant thinks he was afraid that the declarant would force him to return inside the building, our translation).

Em nenhum momento os bombeiros advertiram ou impediram os civis de ingressarem no interior da KISS, o que possibilitou a morte desses indivíduos, alguns depois de cerca de três ou quatro incursões; outros não mais retornavam após entrarem pela primeira vez. (PC - RS, p. 114)

(At no time did the firefighters warn or prevent civilians from entering the interior of the KISS, which led to the deaths of these individuals, some after about three or four entries; others did not return after entering for the first time, our translation).

Photos (clockwise) 1, 2, 3 e 4. Incident Red Zone

Source: VEJA Magazine

However, another complex task was the recovery of the victims' bodies, which required special care due to the adverse conditions of the location. The transport of the bodies to the improvised morgue at Centro Sevi Viero posed a major logistical challenge.

Posteriormente, dúzias de vítimas foram transportadas ao Centro Desportivo Municipal Miguel Sevi Viero em caminhões frigoríficos onde foi improvisado o

necrotério do Instituto Médico Legal. (POLÍCIA CIVIL DE SANTA MARÍA, p. 107-108).

(Subsequently, dozens of victims were transported to the Municipal Sports Center Miguel Sevi Viero in refrigerated trucks, where an improvised morgue of the Institute of Legal Medicine was set up, our translation),

Photo 5. Corpses in the bathroom

Source: NFPA Journal

Photo 6. Morgue at the Municipal Sports Center.

Source: <http://180graus.com/res/imagens/portal/2014/07/18/20130201090137-300x250e.jpg>

Incident Response Analysis

As well as in other similar incidents, such as the *Utopía Nightclub* (Lima, 2022), *The Station Nightclub* (Rhode Island, 2003), and *República de Cromañón* (Buenos Aires, 2004), the first responders face the challenge of balancing competing objectives, such as fighting the fire, rescuing victims, and providing care to mass casualties. The complexity of these incidents

requires efficient coordination among the various response agencies, in addition to the ability to quickly adapt to extreme conditions.

In similar cases, the National Institute of Science and Technology (NIST) comments in its report on the *The Station Nightclub* incident that one of the main difficulties faced by emergency teams was the simultaneous management of multiple tasks and competing objectives.

The concurrent and emerging operational objectives of rescuing victims, providing mass casualty care/transport and mounting an attack to extinguish the fire were apparent to the IC who immediately requested additional assistance. (NIST, 2013p. 56)

Thus, the primary objective in this incident was the search and rescue of victims, as well as the treatment of mass casualties. Although the fire was fought with priority given to rescue, its effectiveness could have been significantly greater. In fact, in Photo 7, it can be seen that the initial attack on the fire was very poor: there is only one water line with low pressure and some firefighters working in the hazard zone without proper personal protective equipment. This scenario highlighted the failure to adhere to operational safety procedures as outlined by NFPA 1500, concerning workplace safety, and NFPA 1710, which addresses the protocol for initial fire attack.

As a mass casualty case, one of the most complex tasks for firefighters was triage, which involves classifying victims based on the severity of their injuries, considering the probability of survival and the available resources at the scene. However, no Victim Concentration Area or Waiting Area was established to organize the multiple resources arriving at the scene. This lack of structure contributed to the overload of the rescue teams. In Photos 1 to 4, the chaotic situation that unfolded during the incident can be observed.

Photo 7. Initial Fire Attack

Source: <http://www.robsonpiresxerife.com/wp-content/uploads/2013/03/BOATE-kiss.jpg>

One of the fundamental elements to be considered from the initial response is operational safety, as established by NFPA 1500 standards. However, at no time did the firefighters implement this function within the Incident Command System (ICS). On the contrary, civilian safety was compromised when they were authorized to enter the hazard zone (red zone) without proper training and without the necessary personal protective equipment. This failure in operational safety management resulted in unnecessary exposure to risk, leading to the deaths of some of these civilian volunteers.

Moreover, the Incident Command System (ICS) was not effectively implemented during the incident. A command post was not established, nor was unified command, and the chain of command was not clearly defined. The absence of a specific action plan for the incident also compromised the organization of the response. Integrated communication between the various agencies involved was inadequate, as pointed out in official reports.

Due to the chaos of the situation, the incident response was largely driven by the initiative of civilian volunteers, who, being numerous, ended up dominating the activities on-site. This occurred instead of following the appropriate standardized procedures for such incidents or yielding leadership to the firefighters, who were responsible for coordinating the operation in a structured manner.

Final Considerations

This study analyzed the application of the Incident Command System (ICS) in the response of the Santa Maria Fire Department, RS, to the Kiss Nightclub fire, which occurred in January 2013. The primary objective of this study was to evaluate the adequacy of the

firefighters' response to the fire in light of the ICS principles, verifying whether the procedures adopted were aligned with the best practices recommended by this system.

The objectives were fully achieved, as it was possible to identify and analyze the procedures followed by the firefighters during the incident and compare them with the standards suggested by the Incident Command System (ICS). The methodology adopted, a qualitative theoretical approach based on a case study, allowed for a detailed analysis of the fire response, providing valuable insights into the failures in emergency management.

From this analysis, several operational errors and safety failures during the fire response were identified. According to the Civil Police reports and other official documents, it became evident that the ICS was not effectively implemented during the incident. Furthermore, the operational safety standards outlined by NFPA 1500 were not followed, compromising the safety of all involved, including firefighters and civilian volunteers. Had these safety protocols and the application of the ICS been properly followed, it would have been possible to save more victims and prevent the deaths of some volunteers who participated in the rescue without proper care and protective equipment.

Thus, the results of this study emphasize the importance of adequate preparation and the implementation of well-structured incident management systems in large-scale emergencies, such as major fires. The rigorous application of these systems is essential to ensure the effectiveness of the response, reduce risks, and protect the safety of everyone involved in rescue and firefighting operations.

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ANNEXES

Annex 1. Infographic of Fire 1

Source: <http://g1.globo.com/rs/rio-grande-do-sul/tragedia-incendio-boate-santa-maria-entenda/platb/>

Annex 2. Infographic of Fire 2

Source: http://www.clicrbs.com.br/sites/swf/tragedia_santa_maria/img/imagem11.jpg

Annex 3. Proposed ICS Organizational Chart for the Kiss Nightclub Incident

Source: Own creation